

Emotional Intelligence and Interpersonal Relationship among the Employees of Public Sector Undertaking

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Abstract:

The aim of the present research is to study the effect of emotional intelligence on interpersonal relationship among the employees of public sector undertaking. To assess the emotional intelligence; Emotional intelligence Scale of Hyde, Pethe and Dhar (2001) and to assess the interpersonal relationship; Fundamental Interpersonal Relationship Orientation-Behavior (FIRO-B) scale of Schutz (1977) used and were administered 30 class four employees from non-technical department of Hindustan Aeronautic Limit (HAL), Ozar Mig (Nashik, Maharashtra). Finding indicate that emotional intelligence positively associated with interpersonal relationship among the employees of public sector undertaking. Significant impact of emotional intelligence on interpersonal relationship found among the employees of public sector undertaking. Emotional intelligence explained 35.60% variance in interpersonal relationship among the employees of public sector undertaking.

Keywords: Emotional intelligence, interpersonal relationship, employees of public sector undertaking.

Introduction:

The growth of any organisation relies heavily on its staff members as one of its most important resources. A high emotional intelligence makes a substantial contribution, not only to pleasant interactions but also to pleasant relationships between people (Wang, 2006). An organisation is a setting in which individuals are required to work effectively with others for extended periods of time. They have a responsibility to cultivate emotional intelligence as well as maintain good relationships with one another.

Emotional Intelligence:

With high emotional intelligence, one is able to accept others' emotions with empathy and feel at ease within interpersonal relationships (Shen, 2005; Hsu, 2013). Emotional intelligence is a capability to prevent 'emotional outbursts' in a passive sense and to develop 'emotional ability' in a positive sense.

The term “emotional intelligence” was introduced by Mayer and Salovey in 1990 from University of Yale. Emotional intelligence defines the ability to perceive emotions, express, regulate your emotion. Another definition formulated by Reuven Bar-On describes emotional intelligence as a series of non-cognitive abilities, competences and skills that influence an individual’s level of adaptability to the demands and pressures of the environment. According to him, emotional intelligence may be divided into five categories, respectively: intrapersonal (emotional self-awareness, assertiveness, self-esteem, self-actualization and independence), interpersonal (empathy, interpersonal relationships and social responsibility), adaptability (problem solving, reality testing, and flexibility), stress management (stress tolerance, impulse control) and general mood (happiness and optimism) (Bar-On, 1997).

Interpersonal Relationship:

An interpersonal relationship is social interaction between two or more people, which involves language, thoughts and emotions and closely correlates with one’s popularity, leadership performance, and agreeableness.

Interpersonal relationship consist of verbal and non-verbal communication skills, relating and collaboration skills, conflict management skills, promoting team spirit, respecting others and being respected. On a complex level, this type of intelligence translates into the individual’s ability to distinguish among the various interpersonal relationships and the ability to respond efficiently to the respective situations, as well as to guess and interpret the hidden reactions of others. (Hatch and Gardner, 1993)

Review of Literature:

Jaeger (2003) posits that emotional intelligence develops over a one’s life span and could be improved through training, teaching and learning in formal educational contexts. Career counselors recognized the importance of emotional intelligence in interpersonal relationship, job satisfaction and well-being (Kidd, 2008). Pool and Sewell (2007) further assert that development of emotional intelligence is required for enhancing persons’ employability and interpersonal relationship.

Individuals’ employability provides an inside sense of stability, security and relates to individual ability to accomplish sustainable employment, interpersonal relationship and move self-sufficiently from within uncertain and unpredictable labor market (Hillage and Pollard, 1998). Furthermore, Puffer, (2011) stated that emotional intelligence positively associate to less dysfunctional career thinking, better career decision-making, self-efficacy, a upper level

of willingness to explore variety of career preferences, and commit to effective interpersonal relationship options. Carson and Carson (1998) further opine that people's emotional intelligence is also positively correlated with important employment experiences and emotional attachment to existing relationship and jobs.

Rationale and Significance of the Study:

In modern era, employees emotional intelligence play vital role at the workplace. Emotional Intelligence is important for understand self and other emotion, regulate emotion, express your emotion. Emotional intelligence seems links with interpersonal behavior. Healthy interpersonal behavior increase productivity in the organization. Emotional intelligence play important role in healthy interpersonal behavior in the organization. Hence the emotional intelligence important for interpersonal behavior in any organization. In the present study, researcher try to find out strength and direction of the emotional intelligence and interpersonal behavior and also try to find out contribution of emotional intelligence in interpersonal behavior among the employees of public sector undertaking. Finding of the present research will be useful for government and non-government organization, institution and counsellor.

Statement of the problem:

“To study the effect of emotional intelligence on interpersonal relationship among the employees of public sector undertaking.”

Objectives:

1. To study the association between emotional intelligence and interpersonal relationship among the public sector undertaking.
2. To study the impact of emotional intelligence on interpersonal relationship among the employees of public sector undertaking.

Hypotheses:

1. There would be positive association between emotional intelligence and interpersonal relationship among the employees of public sector undertaking.
2. There would be significant contribution of emotional intelligence on interpersonal relationship among the employees of public sector undertaking.

Research Design:

It is purely correlation design in which researcher try to find out strength and direction between emotional intelligence and interpersonal behavior. It also aim to assess the contributing of emotional intelligence on interpersonal relationship among the employees of public sector undertaking.

Variables:

Independent Variable: Emotional Intelligence

Dependent Variable: Interpersonal Relationship

Operational Definition:

Emotional Intelligence: Score obtained on factors of emotional intelligence and measured by Emotional Intelligence Scale of Hyde, Pethe and Dhar (2001).

Interpersonal Relationship: Scores obtained on Social Interaction Index factor of Fundamental Interpersonal Relationship Orientation-Behavior (FIRO-B) scale and measured by FIRO-B interpersonal relationship scale of Schutz (1977).

Sample and Data Collection Procedure:

In the present study, total 30 class four (lower rank) male employees collected from non-technical department of Hindustan Aeronautics Limited (HAL) is a public sector organization from Ozar (Mig), Nashik, Maharashtra (India). Age range of employees was from 30 to 50 years. Average age range was 39.14 year. They administered the set of inventories including personal data sheet and asked them to fill in questionnaires independently.

Tools of the Study:

Researcher used the following tools-

1. Emotional Intelligence Scale (2001):

The emotional intelligence scale was developed by Hyde, Pethe and Dhar (2001). The 34 items constituting the emotional intelligence questionnaire and each item has five alternatives-“Strongly agree”, “Agree”, “Uncertain”, “Disagree”, and “Strongly disagree”. The respondent have to select an alternative by putting a across in the respective column. Scoring key is used the item high scores corresponds to high emotional intelligence.

2. Fundamental Interpersonal Relationship Orientation-Behavior (1992) (FIRO-B):

Fundamental Interpersonal Relationship Orientation-Behavior (FIRO-B) is developed by Schutz (1992), consisted 54 items were classified six cell from two dimension interpersonal area and direction of the behavior. The mean coefficient stability of the six scale is .76.

Result and Interpretations:

Obtained result shown that correlation between emotional intelligence and interpersonal relationship found $r=0.60$ which is significant at 0.001 level. It indicate that emotional intelligence and interpersonal relationship positively associated with each other. First hypothesis stating that “There would be positive association between emotional intelligence and interpersonal relationship among the employees of public sector undertaking” is accepted. To calculate linear regression, correlation must be significant. Here, correlation between emotional intelligence and interpersonal relationship found $r=0.60$ which is significant at 0.001 level. Hence the linear regression has been done. Simple linear regression calculated to predict interpersonal relationship based on emotional intelligence. For emotional intelligence as the independent or predicted variable, the obtained value of adjusted $R^2=0.356$, and $F= 15.486$, $p<0.001$, $\beta= .597$, $p<.001$. The obtained results indicate that emotional intelligence explained 35.60% variance in interpersonal relationship among the employees of public sector undertaking. Second hypothesis stating that “There would be significant contribution of emotional intelligence on interpersonal relationship among the employees of public sector undertaking” is accepted.

Conclusion:

1. Emotional intelligence and interpersonal intelligence found positively correlated among the employees of public sector undertaking.
2. Significant impact of emotional intelligence on interpersonal relationship found among the employees of public sector undertaking. Emotional intelligence explained 35.60% variance in interpersonal relationship among the employees of public sector undertaking.

Limitations:

1. Present study cannot be generalized on female employees.
2. For the present study, only class four employees selected from public sector undertaking.
3. Sample size in the present study only 30.

Suggestions:

1. Female employees can be consider in the future study.
2. Higher or other rank of employees can be considered in the study.
3. Comparative study can be consider with large sample size.

Implications:

It is necessary to develop emotional intelligence in order to successfully maintain interpersonal relationships within the workplace. Since the definition of emotional intelligence states that you need to be able to express and regulate your emotions as well as understand both your own and the emotions of others. After that, you will be able to perform or engage with one another more effectively. As a result, emotional intelligence has a significant impact on the quality of interpersonal connections.

References:

- Bar-On, R. (2000). Emotional and social intelligence: insights from the emotional quotient inventory, in R. Bar-On and J.D.A. Parker (Eds.), Handbook of emotional intelligence. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.
- Goleman, D. (1998). Working with emotional intelligence. London: Bloomsbury Publishing.
- Hatch, T. & Gardner, H. (1993). 'Finding cognition in the classroom: an expanded view of human intelligence' in G. Salomon (ed.) Distributed Cognitions. Psychological and educational considerations, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Salovey, P. & Mayer, J. D. (1990). Emotional Intelligence. Imagination, Cognition and Personality. 9 (3), pp.185-211.
- Tsui-shuang, W., Chun-pao, I. and Chung-I, H. (2014). Emotional intelligence and interpersonal relationships of college students in Southern Taiwan. Universal Journal of Management 2(8): 133- 138. <http://www.hrpub.org>.